

Translation of ecological terms from English into Uzbek: challenges and strategies

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Abstract

Translating ecological terminology from English into Uzbek presents a series of linguistic and cultural challenges. This article examines these challenges and proposes strategies to ensure accurate and effective translation. By addressing lexical gaps, structural differences, and cultural nuances, translators can enhance the clarity and relevance of ecological communication. The article also highlights best practices and methodologies for overcoming these challenges, ensuring that ecological information is accessible and understandable for Uzbek learners.

Keywords: *ecological terminology, translation challenges, linguistic differences, cultural nuances, effective communication, uzbek translation*

Translation is a cornerstone of globalization, enabling the exchange of knowledge, culture, and technology across linguistic boundaries. As the world becomes increasingly interconnected, the demand for accurate and effective translation services grows, facilitating international collaboration and understanding. Ecological terminology is also becoming increasingly important as global awareness of environmental issues rises. This article explores the linguistic challenges, effective translation strategies, and cultural considerations involved in this complex task.

According to Cronin, *“Ecology has become a central question governing the survival and sustainability of human societies, cultures and languages”* [4, P. 1]. Accurate translation of the ecological terms ensures that scientific

knowledge and ecological initiatives can be effectively communicated across different languages and cultures, fostering global environmental actions. In Uzbekistan, the translation of ecological terminology is crucial for raising awareness and promoting sustainable practices. As the country faces unique environmental challenges, clear and accurate communication of ecological concepts is essential for effective policy-making and public education.

The translation of ecological terms involves several significant challenges that must be addressed to ensure accurate communication. When there is a geographical gap between languages, there tends to be ecological diversity, which leads to a translation problem because of the “*cultural gap or distance between the source and target languages*” [5, P. 94]. According to Karen Hodges, misinterpretations in terms of standardization of terminology related to the environment in the scientific field should not be directed to the fact the terms being “polysemous but rather to the lack of contextual or explicit clues that identify which meaning is intended” [2, P. 37]. Therefore, one of the primary challenges in translating ecological terms is the absence of direct equivalents in Uzbek. For example, the term "sustainable development" lacks a straightforward counterpart, necessitating the creation of new phrases or compound words to convey the intended meaning accurately [3, P. 50].

Structural differences between languages can significantly impact the translation process. The differences in grammar and syntax between English and Uzbek complicate the translation process because one of the unique linguistic features of ecological terms is that they often contain compound words and compound (two-component, three-component, four-component) terms. It is determined by the two main aspects: the first one is that the formation process is taking place in the eco-terminological system of Uzbek language and, the second factor is the presence of eco-terminological lacunas related to the first one [1, P. 452]. English ecological terms are often concise and multi-faceted, whereas Uzbek translations may require more descriptive and elaborate

expressions. For instance, the expression “*Assessment of the environment (or its components)*” needs a change of forms in the words because of its differences in the languages used in the scientific texts.

Finding lexical equivalents for English ecological terms in Uzbek is a significant challenge. This involves identifying words in the target language that convey the same meaning and connotation as those in the source language. To address lexical gaps, translators often need to develop new Uzbek equivalents for English ecological terms. This process involves coining new words or adapting existing ones to ensure clarity and precision. For example, the term “*biologic diversity*” has been translated as “*Biologik xilma-hillik*” which keeps the clarity, but has the equivalent in Uzbek now [7, P. 57]. Another example of conveying the identical meaning can be observed in “*Disturbed lands*”, meaning plots which have lost in result of their usage their original economic value and frequently they become a source of negative environmental impact, as “*Ishdan chiqqan yerlar*” even though the word “*disturbed*” has a different notion in various contexts [7, P. 119].

Translators must also consider the context in which ecological terms are used, adapting translations to fit cultural and contextual specifics. This approach ensures that the translations are meaningful and relevant to the target audience. For instance, the concept of “*Excise duty and tax*” might require additional research because the term “*duty*” is not what the term ordinary students could understand in the ecological context - “*Aksiz yig'implari va soliqlari*” [7, P. 15].

Collaborating with subject matter experts and native speakers can enhance the accuracy and cultural relevance of translations. Experts can provide insights into the nuances of both languages, ensuring that ecological terms are translated effectively. This collaboration is crucial for complex and technical terms. Terms such as “*Abatis*” which can be difficult to translate into Uzbek since its scientific novelty to the translator can be translated properly as

“*Kesinti*” having discussed with an expert who is aware of their field [7, P. 124].

To deal with structural and grammatical challenges translators usually face, they need to analyze the grammar features of the target language to reach the high accuracy in the translation. For example, converting passive constructions into active ones to fit Uzbek grammatical norms can help accurately convey the original message. “*Forests are being depleted*” could be translated as “*O'rmonlar kamayib bormoqda*” since English often utilizes the passive voice to describe ecological processes, whereas Uzbek prefers active constructions. Similar process could be observed in the change of noun forms in the terms into predicate noun in Uzbek translation because Uzbek language cannot fit the structural peculiarities of English ecological terms in other ways. “*Atrof-muhit (yoki uning komponentlari) holatini baholash*” is the vivid example of the above-mentioned concept where word formation in the case of “*assessment*” changes into “*baholash*” from the source text “*Assessment of the environment (or its components)*” [7, P. 30].

To summarize, an accurate and effective translation of environmental terms from English into Uzbek is crucial for raising environmental awareness and implementing sustainable practices in Uzbekistan. Given the linguistic and cultural differences between the two languages, translators play a vital role in bridging this gap. They should use appropriate strategies to ensure the accuracy of the translation.

This process involves a thorough examination of lexical gaps, structural differences, and cultural nuances. By creating new terms or adapting existing ones and working closely with experts in the field, translators can improve the quality of translation of environmental terminology. In addition, constant research and professional development are necessary in order for translators to be aware of changing terminology and improve their methods. Ultimately,

successful translation of environmental terms allows native Uzbek speakers to understand and participate in critical environmental issues.

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